

VLC over High-Flux LEDs Using Simple Baseband Signaling: Spectral Stitching vs. Beam Combining

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Abstract: Ethernet-over-VLC transmission is accomplished over medium- and high-flux (>50lm) LEDs, revealing that broadband modulation with simple coding prevails over distortion-sensitive modulation techniques. Towards that, a sub-20lm LED can cater for 100-m real-time LiDAR point-cloud transmission.

1. Introduction

Optical wireless communications (OWC) is an attractive and license-free alternative for RF-based wireless access, mostly due to its compatibility with high user densities and electro-magnetic interference [1]. Possible OWC scenarios include in-door deployments, the wireless point-to-point backhaul or communication between mobile users. Given the widespread use in consumer applications, light emitting diodes (LED) are ideal candidates for low-cost visible-light communication (VLC) implementations. As abundant as LEDs are, as versatile is their adoption as luminaire, as emitter for joint illumination and communication [2], or as optical receiver [3]. The most pertinent parameter towards a choice in favor of VLC is its achievable data rate. Even though micro-LEDs offer large electro-optic bandwidths in the GHz range [4-6], their light characteristics primarily resort to the short- λ (in)visible spectral region and thus a low luminous flux of less than 0.1 lm (Fig. 1a). This renders them incompatible for simultaneous lighting. On the other hand, high-flux LEDs face an intrinsic bandwidth limitation, which primarily results from the larger junction depletion and diffusion capacitances of its large-area die and the series resistance introduced due to ohmic contacts, while bonding parasitics further contribute to a steep roll-off in their electro-optic response [7].

This work investigates the trade-off between luminous flux and high-rate on-off keyed (OOK) transmission when adopting high-power LEDs used in lighting applications. Frequency-stitched data transmission is compared to incoherent power combination in multi-element VLC transmitter configurations, revealing that the advantage of a high flux is eroded by the sensitivity of bandwidth-extending modulation concepts to non-linear distortion. Finally, out-door point-cloud data transmission is demonstrated in real-time over a 100-m Ethernet-over-VLC link.

2. Spectrally Stitched Bandwidth vs. Combination of Lower-Power Beams

To overcome the intrinsic bandwidth and power limitation of LED technology, a multi-element emitter (Fig. 1b) is considered to (i) leverage the transmit power through incoherent beam combining and (ii) to extend the bandwidth through spectral stitching. While the first aspect is straight-forward and can be directly employed for LEDs with a sufficiently wide bandwidth, the spectral decomposition of a broadband data signal into multiple concatenated frequency bands can provide such a bandwidth if the “slow” LEDs feature a smooth roll-off in their response. As Fig. 1a shows, the 6dB-bandwidth f_{6dB} of high-power LEDs (LED-**M** with 18 lm at 120 mA, LED-**H** with 52 lm at 350 mA) extends well beyond their 3dB-bandwidth f_{3dB} . For a constant roll-off and $f_{6dB} \geq 2f_{3dB}$, the effective 3dB bandwidth of a stitched e/o response can be extended to at least $N \cdot f_{3dB}$ (Fig. 1b, **H**) when employing N LEDs for the VLC emitter. Simple OOK can then be used in combination with analogue filtering embedded in the driver circuit, instead of resorting to DSP-based multi-carrier modulation formats that come at a significant increase in complexity.

Figure 1c presents the experimental setup for evaluating the compatible optical budget for these two transmitter configurations based on high-power LED technologies. Each VLC transmitter builds on three red (634 nm) LED emitters that are either individually driven by the respective band of the frequency-stitched data signal (LED-**H**) or by the same data signal (LED-**M**), according to their electro-optic response (Fig. 2a). The intrinsic 3dB-bandwidth for the LED emitters are 15 (**H**) and 26 MHz (**M**). The rather smooth roll-off in the e/o response motivates the use of an analogue RF equalizer (AEQ) to extend the bandwidth [8]. Even though this AEQ introduces RF loss at the lower frequency range, the beneficial extension of bandwidth to 37 (**H**) and 77 MHz (**M**) trades well against the provision of 6-10 dB of extra gain for the RF driver stage. While for LED-**M** the e/o response already

suits 100 Mb/s modulation, LED-H will resort to a stitched response (ξ in Fig. 2a) to virtually extend its bandwidth to 87 MHz by offsetting the roll-off in its response at the two frequencies $f_1 = 25$ MHz and $f_2 = 50$ MHz.

In both cases, the optical outputs of the constituent LED elements are incoherently combined in power. The launched optical signal is collimated with 2" lens optics and a neutral-density (ND) filter within a lab-scale link is used to set the link budget of the VLC channel. In this way the performance can be evaluated as a function of the budget, which is then related to an equivalent reach following the characterization in Fig. 2b. Here, the beam spot diameter has been acquired over distance and the budget has been calculated according to the geometric loss, considering a 2" lens at the VLC receiver to increase its collection efficiency. The latter builds on an APD+TIA photoreceiver that strikes a balance between a moderate active diameter of $\Phi_{\text{APD}} = 200$ μm and low receiver noise. It has a noise equivalent power (NEP) of <80 fW/√Hz (Fig. 2a), which is supported by a high multiplication corresponding to a responsivity of ~ 33 A/W. The TIA bandwidth has been adjusted to the symbol rate of 100 MHz to enable a high transimpedance gain and thus a good noise performance.

3. Compatible Optical VLC Budget for High-Flux VLC Emitters

Figure 2c shows the received spectrum for frequency-stitched transmission with LED-H. The three individual bands are delimited at f_1 and f_2 . While none of the individual bands (i.e., single LED emitters) yields a useful data signal, the sum of all bands (i.e., all LED outputs) represents the transmitted 100 Mb/s OOK signal with a clearly open eye.

Figure 2d presents the BER performance. For the stitched transmission over LED-H, an optical budget of 21.3 dB can be accomplished at a BER of 10^{-9} (■). Despite the large luminous flux, the optical modulation amplitude is moderate since the stitching of the OOK signal is sensitive to non-linear distortion, which requires to operate the RF drivers in their back-off regime. The broadband-modulated triple-LED-M emitter offers a higher budget of 32.9 dB (●). This is 4.2 dB higher than for a single LED-M (○), which proves the beneficial triple-beam combining to tentatively enable a VLC reach of 157 m (Fig. 2b). The sensitivity of the reception to an angular misalignment α of the receiver is discussed in Fig. 2e. For a focused beam spot at the APD receiver, resulting in an optimally illuminated active area, a BER of 10^{-9} is surpassed for a narrow field-of-view $\text{FoV} = 2\alpha = 0.55^\circ$ (●). When the beam is deliberately defocused to widen its spot, the acceptance angle 2α increases to 1.75° and 3.4° for spot diameters of 2 (▲) and 5 mm (◆), respectively. However, this improvement in alignment tolerance comes at the expense of poor optical coupling and thus with a reduced optical budget: As Fig. 2d shows, a penalty of 6.9 (▲) and 12.2 dB (◆) are incurred for widened beam spots, which would restrict the VLC reach to 69 and 23 m (Fig. 2b). A wider FoV should be instead obtained by employing multi-element VLC receivers [9, 10], which avoid this unfavorable compromise in link budget. However, given the emphasis on realizing a long VLC reach, the FoV is of secondary importance.

Moreover, data has been unidirectionally streamed over the VLC channel using a 100 Mb/s Ethernet link (ϵ in Fig. 1c). Optical protocol termination is employed for the 100 MbE downlink to electrically drive a single LED-M, while the received signal is again fed back to the Ethernet receiver. The 100 MbE uplink was realized with a fiber link. Figure 3a presents the data rate R over a duration of more than 60 mins. Apart from a few isolated rate drops that occur for 0.13% of logged measurements, there is no instability noticed for the LED-based VLC link.

4. LiDAR Point-Cloud Transmission over Out-Door VLC Link Based on Sub-20 Lumen LED

VLC transmission has been finally evaluated in a road-side scenario where LiDAR data is transmitted between two road-side users (RSU) to enable data fusion (Fig. 3b). In this out-door experiment, raw LiDAR data is streamed over a 100 Mb/s Ethernet link that is established over a FSO channel with a reach of 102 m between two stationary RSUs (see Fig. 3c). The VLC transmitter and receiver architectures of Fig. 1c are again employed, specifically with a single LED-M emitter at RSU1. This fully analogue VLC layout with simple OOK modulation supports a low latency for data fusion concerning automotive localization and mapping applications. The received VLC power at RSU2 is tracked through an RSSI monitor for 100 MbE signaling during link detection / negotiation to assist the alignment of the receiver. A 16-channel rotating multi-beam LiDAR (Velodyne VLP-16) at RSU1, operating at 903 nm and having a vertical field-of-view of 30° , then transmits its (downlink) UDP packets over the VLC link for subsequent fusion with local LiDAR data at RSU2. For the sake of simplicity, the (uplink) Ethernet return channel, which solely serves discovery and packet acknowledgement purposes, has been facilitated through OM4 fiber. Out-door measurements at a parking space have been taken during a morning in early summer, at a background illuminance

of 4200 lx.

Figure 4 shows the fused point cloud at RSU2 that results after VLC transmission of LiDAR data from RSU1. The local data at RSU2 has been extended by the domain that is added around RSU1. There is no sector lost during the VLC transmission of acquired LiDAR data, allowing to clearly discern the features around RSU1 (such as B, C, D and E). This proves that a single high-power LED can already cater for LiDAR data relay over a 100-m VLC channel.

5. Conclusion

Ethernet-over-VLC has been evaluated for high-power LEDs. Even though high-flux (>50 lm) LEDs support 100 Mb/s transmission, the higher linearity required for spectral stitching renders their function as VLC emitter less efficient than power-combined medium-flux LEDs. This is underpinned by the capability of a single sub-20lm LED to cater for the needs of real-time LiDAR point-cloud transmission over a 100-m out-door link. Multi-LED power combining can then enable a high margin to overcome bad channel conditions (e.g., poor weather or pick-up of dirt).

6. References

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Fig. 1. (a) State-of-play LED bandwidth and luminous flux. (b) Spectral stitching vs. beam combining. (c) Setup to characterize the VLC budget.

